
20. The Hyades star cluster

THE HYADES STAR CLUSTER is the nearest open cluster to the Sun, at around 45 pc. An arresting sight in the dark night sky, and extending over about 20 degrees, it has been prominent in the development of astronomy over the past hundred years because of its central role in establishing the cosmic distance scale.

Some background on the nature of open star clusters, and their role in the definition of the cosmic distance ‘ladder’, is given under my text on *‘The Distance to the Pleiades’*. Let me just recall that these groups of several hundred stars, formed from the same giant molecular cloud and with roughly the same age, are key objects in the study of stellar evolution because the cluster members are of similar age and chemical composition.

The nearest, notably the Hyades (at about 45 pc) and the Pleiades (at 135 pc), have long been used to calibrate the distances to others more remote, either by matching their main sequences in the Hertzsprung–Russell diagram, or by exploiting the changing geometrical perspective as the entire cluster moves through space.

Since the pioneering work of Lewis Boss (1908) more than a century ago, the Hyades has been the subject of dozens of innovative studies which have refined its distance, and explored the nature of its members through the study of its Hertzsprung–Russell diagram.

BEFORE PUBLICATION of the Hipparcos catalogue in 1997, many studies, using different approaches, had reached on a reasonable consensus in terms of its mean distance. With the Hipparcos parallaxes accurate to around 1 milli-arcsec, distances to individual cluster stars were measured with an accuracy of about 20%. And its mean distance was pinned down, geometrically, as 46.34 ± 0.27 pc for the 100 or so objects within 10 pc of the cluster centre (Perryman et al., 1998).

This result was close to, but much better determined than, that derived from high-precision radial velocity studies, somewhat larger than that from ground-based trigonometric determinations, and slightly smaller than those found from the most up-to-date studies of the cluster’s convergent point.

The Hipparcos studies were in part limited by the pre-selection of stars demanded by the instrument itself, with 240 candidates having been pre-selected, before launch, over some 30–40 degrees on the sky. Their distances and space motions resulted in a total of 140–200 members, depending on the criteria adopted.

Further from the cluster centre, Hipparcos showed a gradual merging between definite cluster members and field stars, both spatially and kinematically. The individual proper motions were fully consistent with a uniform space motion with an internal velocity dispersion of about 0.3 km s^{-1} . The cluster zero-age main sequence could be accurately modelled, based on the estimated helium abundance and isochrone modelling, yielding a cluster age of 625 ± 50 million years.

OBSERVING ALL STARS down to around 20–21 mag, with a much improved accuracy by a factor 10–100, and with its simultaneous high-accuracy photometry, great advances were expected with Gaia, and this has indeed proved to be the case.

Early studies using Gaia DR1, with the TGAS subset, already identified 251 new candidate members (Reino et al. 2018), but deeper insights began with DR2.

Hyades: proper motions (grey) and member positions (colour)

PRE-GAIA, a total of some 800 probable members were known, including a handful of white dwarfs, and a dozen or so brown dwarfs.

The Gaia DR2 analysis by Lodieu et al. (2019) started with all Gaia objects within a 70° radius of the nominal cluster centre, and with a parallax greater than 10 mas (i.e. within 100 pc), resulting in 126 144 objects. An iterative selection based on distances and space motions resulted in 1764 sharing the cluster's mean proper motion. This more than doubles the number of previously known members built up over more than a century.

Further analysis was restricted to objects which they found to be within the core radius of 3.1 pc, the tidal radius of 9 pc, the halo radius of 18 pc, and extending out to a distance limit of 30 pc. This resulted in 85, 381, 568, and 710 sources respectively, while they rejected some 200 objects previously considered as members.

From these stars within the cluster's tidal radius, they derived a mean cluster distance of 47.03 ± 0.20 pc, and a mean space velocity of 46.38 ± 0.12 km s $^{-1}$. They could trace the 3d distribution of stars within the cluster, and could estimate the effects of mass loss over the cluster's lifetime. They could identify clear mass segregation, with the lower mass stars being on average further away from the centre.

Supplemented by infrared photometry, they derived the luminosity and mass functions over the range $G = 3$ –26 mag, corresponding to masses of 2.5–0.04 M_\odot , also showing that their shapes vary as a function of the distances from the cluster centre.

A STUDY OF THE Hertzsprung–Russell diagram of a number of open clusters and globular clusters using the Gaia DR2 data demonstrates the narrow and extremely well-defined main sequence of many of these systems, including the Hyades (Babusiaux et al. 2018). A detailed discussion of the various age estimates for the cluster is taken up by Lodieu et al. (2019).

TWO SEPARATE studies have reported the discovery of remarkable extensions of the cluster's tidal tails using the DR2 data (Röser et al. 2019; Meingast & Alves, 2019). These tails are highly flattened in the Galactic plane, being only about 25 pc in thickness, while extending more than 100 degrees across the sky.

The leading tail, of nearly 300 stars, extends 170 pc from the cluster centre, while the trailing tail with more than 200 stars extends to 70 pc.

This top-down view of the Galactic plane reveals a distinct S-shape to the tails, similar to those observed for some globular clusters, and in excellent agreement with earlier theoretical predictions of their shape, and of their velocity dispersions.

AT THE LOWEST end of the main sequence, some 16 brown dwarfs were known pre-Gaia.

Pérez-Garrido et al. (2018) used the Gaia DR2 data, with 2MASS and WISE infrared photometry, to identify a total of 37 objects whose distances and proper motions are compatible with Hyades membership. Of these, 21 were new. And while Gaia is essentially complete to the hydrogen-burning limit for the Hyades cluster, it is still likely to be incomplete at lower masses.

FOR THE NINE known Hyades white dwarfs, Lodieu et al. (2019) used the Gaia photometry to derive an age of 640^{+67}_{-49} Myr from evolutionary models, in agreement with other methods, including that derived from the lithium-depletion boundary method.

The Hyades white dwarfs also provide a co-eval sample with known distances which can be used to estimate their cooling times and masses. Salaris & Bedin (2018) used the Gaia DR2 astrometry to conclude that a cluster age of 690 Myr yields a slope of the initial–final mass relation closer to other white dwarf determinations.

White dwarf masses can also be derived from their gravitational redshift. The approach is possible in the case of the Hyades because the stellar radial velocities can be deduced from the astrometric data, independently of spectroscopy. Pasquini et al. (2019) found that masses derived from their gravitational redshift estimates are systematically smaller, by 0.02–0.05 M_\odot , than those derived from other methods. Though small, this is a significant finding for white dwarf models.

Confirmed Hyades members from these Gaia DR2 studies are also allowing the properties of nearly 300 X-ray sources discovered with ROSAT, Chandra, and XMM–Newton to be derived (Freund et al. 2020).